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EDUCATION KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

O19 DISSEMINATION & EXPLOITATION PLAN

Project Information

Project acronym:	EKT
Project title:	Education Knowledge Transfer
Agreement number:	612414-EPP-1-2019-1-ES-EPPKA2-KA
Authoring partner:	die Berater Unternehmensberatungs GmbH
Date of preparation:	January 2020

EKT Project Consortium

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The EKT project has been funded with support from the European Commission. This publication reflects the views only of the author, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

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PRESS RELEASES	<i>Fehler! Textmarke nicht definiert.</i>

1. Introduction to Dissemination and Sustainability

Whenever we speak of dissemination and exploitation of project results we refer to activities that are designed to ensure that these results are appropriately recognised, demonstrated and implemented on a wide scale. Dissemination and exploitation are on-going within the project as the majority of outputs will be brought into practice and will be tested and piloted.

This strategy deals with promotion and dissemination that is the basic of successful exploitation later on. It is of crucial importance to achieve the best possible results that all partners involved have the same understanding of key terms.

Dissemination Activities serving the dissemination and exploitation of results are a way to promote the work that has been done as part of the EKT project. Dissemination means to spread widely. This involves spreading the word about the project successes and outcomes as far as possible. Making others aware of the project will have impact on other organisations in the future and will contribute to raising the profile of the organisation carrying out the project.

Dissemination in general is a planned process of providing information to the target group and key actors in regard to project process, activities and results by the use of different dissemination channels at the local, regional, national, EU and international levels.

Sustainability is the capacity of the project to **continue and use its results beyond the end of the funding period**. The project results then can be used and exploited long-term, perhaps via commercialisation, accreditation or mainstreaming. Not all parts of the project or results may be sustainable and it is important to view dissemination and exploitation as a progression that extends beyond the duration of the project, and into the future.

In summary, dissemination and exploitation/sustainability aims to achieve the following objectives:

- To promote and raise awareness with regards to the project contents and developments
- To provide information on the quality, relevance and effectiveness of the results
- To successfully transfer the results to appropriate decision-makers in order to achieve their sustainable promotion and support
- To convince individual end-users to adopt and/or apply the results, also after the project and support by the project partnership has ended

The shared Dissemination Calendar will contain dates and timing of the dissemination activities. It is fundamental that there is common understanding of the aims, because all partners will disseminate information on the project also independently.

The EKT dissemination planning defines its **general aims** as to:

- Generate awareness with regards to the project contents and developments
- Provide information on the quality, relevance and effectiveness of the results
- Make the project well known at regional, local and EU level
- Maintain interest in the project and its developments
- Successfully transfer the results to appropriate decision-makers in order to achieve their sustainable promotion and support
- Share solutions and know how
- Help to bring about action, in particular influencing policy and bringing about change
- Help to develop new partnerships
- Exploit the work of EKT and the products beyond the project's lifetime

1.1 The project overview. What do we want to disseminate?

The project "EKT - Educational Knowledge Transfer" aims to:

- Align the response of ICT companies (in the e-learning sector) with the needs of education in Europe in order to articulate a better response to the challenges facing education today
- Establish a cooperation dynamic between e-learning companies (ICT and service providers) and researchers/education experts (education science faculties) for innovation in higher education and the ICT sector Identify needs of key stakeholders to inform the new programme
- Improve the quality of the university training of student teachers during their professional training period (practical experience period) through the implementation of ICT services and resources, developed jointly between e-learning companies and universities
- Develop new innovative and multidisciplinary approaches to teaching and learning as well as collaboration between universities and enterprises in the development of a comprehensive e-learning technology strategy to be adapted to the needs of the education sector
- Allow the development of a strong collaboration between universities and companies that promotes the joint creation of services based on scientific knowledge and the transfer of educational knowledge to e-learning companies
- Address an unresolved technological problem in e-learning solutions, namely the necessary interoperability of e-learning applications and services

All partners are responsible for national dissemination, in addition to their networking activities, which correspond to their institution profiles. In terms of content, there are some basic principles that should be adopted to ensure an efficient and effective dissemination process:

- Use clear language which suits the target groups. It is important to define and formulate the contents of our project according to the context of our target groups.
- With all publications the defined key messages and advantages of the project results should be taken into account for the respective target groups.
- Quality instead of quantity: the aim of our dissemination activities is explicitly not to send as many emails as possible. Rather, the aim is to approach the right contact persons in the right institutions to ensure a productive exchange about the contents of the project across all countries
- All EKT material/results/communications produced should be published under a unified format both in terms of design and content. A Corporate Identity will be created for the project in order to achieve this unity.
- The publications should be formulated and designed to enable easy adaptation to the different target groups, national backgrounds and contexts.

1.2 Target groups

The most important aspect is to define the target group beforehand in order to make it easier to reach these people. The EKT target groups and multipliers to be reached with dissemination activities are:

- University lecturers and researchers of Education Sciences
- Universities (specially Faculties of Education, University Colleges of Teacher Education).
- Kindergarten, Primary and Secondary Education School teachers.
- Higher Education Students (kindergarten, Primary and Secondary Education prospective European teachers)
- e-learning companies (providers of ICT and services)
- Officials such as school board member
- Teachers unions and other educational organisations

Our target groups will be reached through:

- Dissemination materials i.e. project flyers, presentation templates for conferences and events and other templates for common use by partners (and will be translated in national language).
- EKT website (ektproject.eu) and social media (Facebook and Twitter)
- Stakeholders of the EKT community network
- Project newsletters

- New articles in partner newsletters, news items on the project website and partners' websites
- Press releases
- Scientific articles
- EKT National events

All partners will use their national networks of their organizations for dissemination of information about the project and its results in order to raise awareness about innovative training courses and training materials developed within the project.

Raising awareness and engagement of wide public to use innovative outputs developed within the project will be achieved through two most popular social networks – Facebook and Twitter.

The best way to reach the target group is by providing them with relevant content through different ways like press releases, newsletters, website entries or social media posts. Therefore, it is very important to produce useful and targeted content. This will help you to reach and engage with the target audience.

For example:

- Blog posts and articles – We have to make sure that we write about topics that are of interest to our target audience and are useful to them. Let us highlight the important statements.
- Social media content – Nowadays it is inevitable to use social media. To get the attention a combination of pictures, videos, texts is recommended. Social media content should be posted on a regular basis in order not to lose the access and attention of the target group.

Especially when using social media like Twitter, we have to make sure that we use hashtags in order to get more attention and to reach the target audience. There are different trending hashtags to different topics. On this website you can find trending and useful hashtags for our project. wabisabilearning.com/blogs/technology-integration/100-education-hashtags-educators. The reason we should use hashtags is to make the events, articles, etc easier to discover for interested people.

Besides the online distribution, a certain face to face distribution is also important. Within the scope of this project, flyers are created and translated into the local language. Take and distribute the flyers at different events and network meetings you participate in.

Stakeholders

Identify the stakeholders in your country and get in direct contact with them. Stakeholders have an outreach that will help you to spread information about the project. In regard to EKT stakeholders can be for example educators, principals, school boards or collective entities like committees, teacher and student organisations.

A template is provided to fill in all relevant information like e-mail addresses, website, etc. of stakeholders. Due to privacy rules, each partner can keep their own stakeholder list. Only distribute the first page of the template document with partners, which contains the number of stakeholders you have reached.

1.3 Project Results

Project milestones and outcomes are important as they determine dissemination activities. All partners will be expected to disseminate main results through their institutional dissemination channels and beyond.

The following are project milestones, which will need to be disseminated:

- Report on in-school teaching practice (in-school placement) needs and possibilities of the technologies
- Report on Educational and technological framework for development of professional competences in in-school placement
- Technical analysis report: Infrastructure definition and guidelines
- Advanced e-learning system for in-school placement
- A Mobile app
- A Small private online course (SPOC) for teachers (School tutors), Students (prospective teachers) and university lecturers (university tutors)
- Pilot report

2. Dissemination in the EKT project

Each partner is responsible for dissemination at local, regional and national level and this will be monitored and coordinated by *die Berater*® across the partner countries.

As we have already established, it is much more effective to build up productive contacts with the right stakeholders and networks who themselves possess good networks and communication channels. Thus, personal networks and contacts, which are already available within the EKT consortium, would be optimal for this purpose. For this reason, each of the partners will create a contact database, which will include the most relevant stakeholders and network of partners that will receive updates on the project and other information that might interest them and encourage their active participation in further promotion of the project.

However, the internal contacts of the consortium will certainly not be sufficient enough for successful dissemination. In this section we will therefore clarify which media are best suited to project dissemination purposes. Tips are provided to ensure optimal and effective application of each method of dissemination. A detailed reporting and evaluation concept will ensure that dissemination activities can be regularly checked and optimised.

The creation of the visual identity of the project is fundamental for the project dissemination:

Corporate Identity Elements

- Project Logo
- Web design
- Word template
- PowerPoint template

It is highly recommended to use the corporate design in all material produced within the project to support project recognition. In addition, it is of crucial importance to follow the rules of corporate identity given by the European Commission such as clear instructions on the use of logos and disclaimers. In order to provide an overview we have divided the dissemination activities into four main groups:

- **Internet based activities:** This includes the EKT website and social media i.e. the EKT Facebook page, partner newsletters, news features on partners' websites, social media posts, etc.
- **Face-to-face activities:** These will include all foreseen events and conferences including the national and transnational training activities
- **Media based activities:** Dissemination through press releases, scientific articles etc.
- **Other activities** These include all other activities such as dissemination through TV and radio (mainly on local/regional level), webinars, etc.

Dissemination Recording

An Excel table was created for the recording of the dissemination activities. The dissemination recordings have to be filled in, updated and uploaded continuously from the beginning to the end of the project. This table is available for each partner in the folder. The purpose is to disseminate information about the EKT project at various events, presentations, Facebook pages of partner organizations and suchlike. These must be recorded with evidence (screenshot, photographs, etc.). Information such as target group, date, and reach must also be provided.

The Excel spreadsheet is reviewed on a quarterly basis by *die Berater*[®] and feedback is also given to the partners.

2.1 Internet based activities

Project website at ektproject.eu

die Berater[®] will be responsible for the development and maintenance of the official project website and project Facebook and Twitter accounts.

The project website will be available in the partner languages (English, Italian, Romanian, Bulgarian, Spanish/Basque). The website will contain general project information and specific information about the EKT products and reports developed. The website will have direct access to the EKT Facebook page and will act as the main place for all important information on the project rationale, aims, objectives, target groups, activities and results as well as information about each partner organisation.

EKT partners' websites

Every project partner will publish an introductory presentation/summary of the EKT project on their own organisational/institutional websites in their respective country language – to acknowledge the project contents, the EKT programme, the aims, the target groups and the project results. In this way, the networks and stakeholders of all project partners will be effectively informed about EKT. Links to the official project website and to other partners' sites and social media will extend this information network.

News and Articles

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Starting with the second year of the project, the website will be updated by *die Berater*[®] monthly with an article from the partners. For this it is important that especially partners at events, pilots or presentations of the project write a short report and then upload text and pictures separately into the folder "**website_news**". To ensure that these articles are written similarly, the following is important:

- Photograph (of the event or presentation) or picture (diagram or self-created graphic)
- Title and Text (max 350 words)

Each partner is required to write a short report on their own events and presentations in their own country, send it to *die Berater*[®], so that the articles can be published on our website.

Apart from that, articles can also be written about

- Project meetings
- Upcoming events and pilotings
- Current status of the project
- Relevant information and news about the project

Project Newsletters

Overall three project news bulletins in English will be created during the project lifetime. As well as providing information on the progress of project activities the newsletters will give some insight into the aims of the project overall. The project news/bulletin will be published via the EKT website, all project partners will contribute to the content of the newsletter.

It is recommended that partners also use the tool of a national newsletter (with a link to the general newsletter) to inform their national and local stakeholders and target groups of current project activities and products.

The project newsletter is distributed every 6 months by all partners. The newsletter is written in English by *die Berater*[®] and will be adapted and edited in close collaboration with all partners. *Die Berater*[®] will take the information from the news-articles from the website and summarise it. Partners can make contributions, edit and give feedback on it.

The project newsletter will be sent two weeks before it is published to partners for revision. Estimated time schedule for sending the newsletter follows below.

All partners are asked to translate the newsletter into their own national language and send it to their own newsletter subscribers. We will have 5 project newsletter which at around these dates:

1. Newsletter: November 2020
2. Newsletter: May 2021
3. Newsletter: November 2021
4. Newsletter: May 2022
5. Newsletter: October 2022

EKT Facebook page facebook.com/projectekt

The EKT Facebook page will be a very useful tool for the partnership to keep the project alive by regular posts about the project and other related topics that the project addresses. This will ensure a wider visibility and more active involvement of stakeholders. The project website will be connected to the Facebook page, to enable updates to be easily received by those liking the EKT Facebook page.

The content will consist of a combination of images and text to get the attention of the users. Hashtags that will be used are #education #learning #knowledge. These are trending hashtags, that will help us to reach the target audience. In addition, we will add the tag #ektproject.

Additional hashtags can be applied. The popularity of certain hashtags can change within a short time. Therefore, it is important to use current and alternating tags, which are of course related to the project itself.

All partners will also share selected postings of the project facebook page on their own social media pages. Starting with year two of the project, each partner will produce one facebook posting per year (this can contain the same content as a recent newsletter content). *Die Berater*[®] will coordinate the months through the shared calendar to distribute the news updates as evenly as possible.

2.2 Media based activities:

On the national level, partners will disseminate project information through:

- Press releases
- Scientific articles

2.3 Face-to-face activities

Partners will also disseminate project information through:

- Presentations in conferences and events
- EKT National events

3. Dissemination on different levels

3.1 Dissemination activities planned at the European level

At the European level the project coordinator/WPL for Dissemination will make sure the consortium

- creates the main dissemination products mentioned above
- publish three project newsletters
- each establish a European dissemination list
- identify relevant internet platforms and other means of promotion at European level

3.2 National dissemination activities planned

Each project partner will

- place information about the project on its website and link it to the project web platform
- identify key players in the field of gender based violence and social services in their country
- create national contact lists of stakeholders (dissemination lists), inform and consult them regularly
- circulate at least 3 electronic newsletters at significant project milestones among the institutions and individuals on their contact lists
- present the project at regional, local or national events related to the project
- establish contacts to local, regional and national media
- regularly contribute to the social media presence (according to the social media plan)

The following activities are planned in four main levels by partnership:

ORGANIZATIONAL LEVEL

No	Activity, tool/ channel	Date	Responsible partner
1.	Project logo and website (<i>information on the project aims, activities, the partner institutions and the project outcomes, publish public outcomes</i>)	January 2020	<i>die Berater</i> [®]
2.	Information about the project on the websites of each organizations	February 2020	All partners
3.	News article for website (<i>every partner has to write at least 2 articles about their current project status in their country, events, ..</i>)	November 2020 – October 2022	All partners
4.	Dissemination of information about the project and its results (delivery of information)	February 2020 - October 2022	All partners

No	Activity, tool/ channel	Date	Responsible partner
5.	Regular project dissemination on organizations Facebook pages and through other social media (<i>Tweeter, LinkedIn, etc.</i>)	September 2020 – October 2022 (After each international partner meeting, preparation of IO. After the Learning/training/teaching activity; multiplier events, the Final conference, etc.)	All partners

REGIONAL/NATIONAL LEVEL

No.	Activity, tool/ channel	Date	Responsible partner
1.	Promoting the project at national events <i>(seminars, conferences, workshops, meetings, etc.)</i>	November 2020 – October 2022	All partners
2.	Promoting Project's Facebook page at national level, including organisations outside the official partnership	March 2020 - August 2022	All partners
3.	Multiplier events <i>(disseminate project results)</i>	September 2019 - September 2022	All partners
4.	Publications, press releases scientific contributions (publications, papers, conferences)	September 2019 - September 2022	All partners

No.	Activity, tool/ channel	Date	Responsible partner
5.	<p>Project Newsletter (NL) distributed every 6 months</p> <p>Newsletter will be translated by every partner in their own languages.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. NL = November 2020 2. NL = May 2021 3. NL = November 2021 4. NL = May 2022 5. NL = September 2022 - October 2022 	<p>die Berater® in collaboration with all partners</p>

EUROPEAN/INTERNATIONAL LEVEL

o.	Activity, tool/ channel	Date	Responsible partner
1.	Promoting of the project's web-site at European/International levels	February 2020 - October 2022	All partners
2.	<p>Providing information about the project through different networks and international events to organisations outside the official partnership on international level</p> <p>Networks like</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Educational Research Association (EERA) eera-ecer.de • World Education Research Association (WERA) weraonline.org • American Educational Research Association (AERA) aera.net • Spanish Pedagogical Society (SEP) sepedagogia.es/?lang=en • Association for the Development of Educational Technology and New Technologies Applied to Education 	November 2020 - September 2022	All partners

o.	Activity, tool/ channel	Date	Responsible partner
	<p>(EDUTEC) edutec.es</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mexican Council for Educational Research (COMIE) comie.org.mx/v4 • ÖFEB (Austrian Society for Research and Development in Education) oefeb.at/veranstaltungen <p>Events like</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BET in London • OnlineEDUCA Berlín, • EDUTEC Spain and latin America, • SIMO, Madrid. • Learning Technologies in Paris, • WERA Annual meeting/Conference, • AERA Annual meeting/Conference, • ECER Annual meeting /Conference, • XVII Congreso Nacional de Pedagogía (SEP) 2020, • IX Congreso Iberoamericano de Pedagogía (SEP) 2020. • EduDays (https://www.edudays.at/) • Österreichischer Schulleiterkongress (Austrian School Principals' Congress http://www.österreichischer- 		

o.	Activity, tool/ channel	Date	Responsible partner
	schulleitungskongress.at/		
3.	Promoting Project's Facebook page at European/International level	March 2020 - October 2022	All partners
4.	Two publications on EPALE platform	January 2021 – October 2022	die Berater®
5.	Publication and promotion of the handbook	Juni 2022 – October 2022	die Berater®, All partners
6.	Final European conference	September 2022 - October 2022	USC, All partners
7.	Placing information on Erasmus+ program Projects results platform: ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/projects	September 2022 - October 2022	USC

Important reminder:

All partners are responsible for the content of their own publications. The European Commission support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents which reflects the views only of the authors, and the **Commission cannot be held responsible for any use** which may be made of the information contained therein.

Erasmus+ funding disclaimer must be used and referenced at dissemination events. The project logo should also be clearly visible.

As evidence we consider **attendance lists signed by participants, screenshots and photographs**. These documents must all be recorded with an exact date.

4. Exploitation of the EKT project

The following exploitation mechanisms will be used:

- **Transfer and follow-up projects:** Partners who completed the EKT experimentation will be asked to investigate further and continue the pilot on a bigger scale, modified as appropriate from the learning experience.
- **Networking:** Partners are asked to get in contact with relevant policy makers, elearning companies and other education sectors, informing them about the results of the pilot and the project recommendations in relation to Initial Teacher Education (specially in-school teaching practices).

1. Accessibility, Implementation and Improvement

The project results will be maintained on the project website and also be spread through national and European web portals to ensure that the project results are visible and accessible for everyone. The target groups should have access to the outputs and products, be able to learn from them, modify them according to their own needs. The goal is that the target group works with the results and takes them to the next level.

An important element of the exploitation of our project results, the Handbook for in-school teaching practice (in-school placement) in European Initial Teacher Education will be available for download from our website. It will be distributed under a license which allows users to copy and distribute the material.

EKT aims to ensure that the results can be used at national/regional level and that the methodologies are integrated into the teacher education. Therefore, the partners will use the outcomes of the project to

disseminate the results to policy makers, government authorities and universities in order to provide ideas about the best way to develop in-school placement.

2. Support and Representation

Participating countries will also continue to support the pilot school project teams in disseminating innovative practices within schools. For this purpose, the partner organizations may envisage setting up a network to provide support for promoting the pilot and follow-up results at national level. Their support and expertise in implementing the EKT methodology and advanced e-learning system.

3. Sustainability

In many cases, sustainability is often overlooked as a success factor and is often seen as an attribute of "effectiveness". Sustainability needs to be integrated into the project from the very beginning, and an evaluation of sustainability requires a separate set of criteria. Several factors, such as the design of the project outcomes, the involvement of stakeholders, and the institutional and organizational capacity of the project partners, will all have an impact on the sustainability potential of the project, and the activities must be evaluated based on their focus on a sustainability perspective.

BOSS Factor Analysis

In the EKT project, we are implementing the *BOSS Factor Analysis* to assess and **evaluate** the sustainability.

The term *BOSS – Beginning of Sustainability Status* goes back to the sociologist Marcus Ingle (Portland State University). The application of the *BOSS Factor Analysis* approach to evaluation of transnational EU-funded projects was developed by Paul Talbot (*die Berater*[®]).

BOSS Factor Analysis is based on a few general assumptions:

- ❖ The main purpose of (EU) projects is to bring about lasting change to an identified problem. In the case of EKT: to promote excellence in initial teacher training, so that we help overcome the false prejudice that understands that future teachers learn the skills necessary to exercise their profession naturally just by being placed in a school. It is also the aim of the project to reach a sustainable implementation of the programme and all related activities.
- ❖ Most projects do not focus on the lasting change they want to bring about, but on mere completion of the deliverables promised in the project proposal. This is one reason why many projects fail to make sure that these outputs will be used by the target groups after the end of funding.
- ❖ The isolation of project objectives is another reason why sustainability often fails. In many cases, the project is not directly linked to the overarching strategic goals of the participating partner institutions. We believe that only if a project manager succeeds in aligning the project objectives with some of the institution's strategic goals is it likely that the project results will be used systematically after the project is over.

- ❖ A project manager aiming for sustainability should identify and continuously and actively influence crucial *BOSS* factors throughout the project's lifetime.
- ❖ To accomplish sustainability of project results the end of the project should be seen as the beginning of sustainability. This *Beginning of Sustainability Status (BOSS)* is determined by a number of internal and external factors (*BOSS* factors) which have to be in favour of the project's aims:

Internal factors	External factors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • commitment • usability • quality criteria • marketing strategy • trained staff • learner motivation • supportive local network • ... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • compliance • state subsidies • demand • integration in curriculum • reputation • visibility • recognition of programme • ...

Application of the *BOSS Factor Analysis* in EKT

Partners are kindly asked to follow these steps:

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EKT - BOSS FACTOR Analysis: Tool 1

- Identify strategic aim(s) of your institution to which you can align the EKT project goals.
- Describe how specific EKT outcomes can contribute to these strategic aims.
- Identify internal and external BOSS factors (people in the organisation, stakeholders, political environment, existing programmes, colleagues' attitudes etc.), which need to be addressed to bring EKT outcomes and strategic aims together. Rate the factors' importance and concentrate on the most important ones in the future.

EKT - BOSS FACTOR Analysis: Tool 2

- Select the most important BOSS FACTORS and draft an Action Plan with concrete measures you will take to influence these factors positively, incl. the person responsible and the timing (EKT BOSS FACTOR Analysis: Tool 2)

EKT - BOSS FACTOR Analysis: Tool 3

- Monitor and document the results of the actions taken, and of challenges encountered and how they could be solved.

Template BOSS Factor Analysis

EKT - BOSS FACTOR Analysis: Tool 1

Potential contribution of project outcomes to long-term objectives of your organisation

Long-term objective of organisation	Project outcome	Internal BOSS factors	Rating (1-10)	External BOSS factors	Rating (1-10)	

Comments and explanations:

EKT - BOSS FACTOR Analysis: Tool 2

Action Plan

BOSS factor	Action	Responsible	Time	Result	Done

Comments and explanations:

EKT - BOSS FACTOR Analysis: Tool 3

Monitoring of Action Plan

Time period: _____

BOSS factor	Action taken	Challenges encountered / solutions found	Result	Done

Comments and explanations:

The BOSS factor analysis will be used for the continuous monitoring of the project. The project partners will be asked to identify internal and external BOSS factors (people in the organisation, stakeholders,

political environment, existing programmes, etc.), which need to be addressed to bring EKT outcomes and strategic aims together, at three times during the project: Each at the the of year 1 (October 2020), year 2 (October 2021) and year 3 (October 2022).

Annex: Templates and Logos for use in the EKT project

Logo

Visibility of the EU funding

Disclaimer

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In separate files on the Project Nextcloud:

- **Template for publications, reports**
- **Template for word documents**
- **Template for Power Point Presentations**

